

Emotional Intelligence and Burnout among Pre-Service Teachers

Vipin Singh¹, Nivedita Shah², Dr. Sarika Mittal³

¹ Research Scholar, HNBGU Central University, Srinagar, Garhwal

² Research Scholar, HNBGU Central University, Srinagar, Garhwal

³ Associate Professor, Ras Bihari Bose Subharti University, Dehradun

Corresponding Author Email: Vipinrawat.edu@gmail.com

Abstract

This study examines emotional intelligence and burnout among pre-service teachers during their training period. A mixed-methods approach was used to understand both the levels of emotional intelligence and burnout, as well as experiences related to stress. The sample consisted of 77 B.Ed. and M.Ed. students from one central and one private university. Data were collected using the Emotional Intelligence Scale (EIS-SANS), a self-developed burnout scale, and open-ended questions. The results showed moderate levels of emotional intelligence and burnout among the participants. A significant negative relationship was found between the two variables, indicating that pre-service teachers with higher emotional intelligence experienced lower burnout. The qualitative findings revealed that heavy academic workload, teaching practice, and personal responsibilities were the main causes of burnout. Participants reported using simple coping strategies such as planning their work, taking short breaks, and seeking support from peers. The study highlights the role of emotional intelligence in reducing burnout and suggests that teacher education programmes should pay greater attention to emotional well-being during training.

Keywords: Emotional Intelligence, Burnout, Pre-service Teachers, Teacher Education, Mixed-Method Study, Emotional Well-being

Introduction

Teachers are expected to demonstrate not only pedagogical competence but also emotional stability while managing diverse academic and interpersonal responsibilities. In India, recent reforms in teacher education have emphasized both professional quality and teacher well-being, making the pre-service phase a critical stage of professional formation. During this period, teacher trainees engage in academic coursework, school-based teaching practice, and evaluation processes that may generate academic demands and role-related stress.

Emotional Intelligence (EI), defined as the ability to perceive, understand, and regulate one's own and others' emotions (Salovey & Mayer, 1997), is considered essential for coping with professional challenges and sustaining effective relationships. Research suggests that pre-service teachers often exhibit moderate levels of EI, indicating the need for its systematic integration within teacher education programmes (Alluru & Suneela, 2023; Madhur, 2017).

Burnout, characterized by emotional and mental exhaustion resulting from prolonged stress (Pines & Aronson, 1988), has increasingly been observed even during the training stage. Academic workload, teaching practice, and institutional expectations may contribute to burnout among pre-service teachers. Prior studies have consistently reported a negative association between emotional intelligence and burnout, suggesting that higher EI may

function as a protective factor against stress and exhaustion (Kant & Shanker, 2021). However, empirical evidence focusing specifically on pre-service teachers within the contemporary Indian teacher education context remains limited, underscoring the need to examine this relationship during the training phase to better understand their professional preparedness and well-being.

Research questions

- What are the levels of emotional intelligence among pre-service teachers?
- What are the levels of burnout among pre-service teachers?
- What is the significant relationship between emotional intelligence and burnout among pre-service teachers?
- What early signs of burnout do pre-service teachers identify, and what strategies do they use to prevent or manage it?
- How do pre-service teachers understand and provide emotional support to their peers?

Objectives of the study

- To assess the levels of emotional intelligence among pre-service teachers.
- To assess the levels of burnout among pre-service teachers.
- To examine the relationship between emotional intelligence and burnout among pre-service teachers.
- To identify the early signs and causes of burnout experienced by pre-service teachers and the strategies they use to manage or prevent it.
- To understand how pre-service teachers perceive the emotions of their peers and provide emotional support.

Hypotheses

- There is no significant relationship between total emotional intelligence and total burnout among pre-service teachers.
- There is no significant difference in burnout levels among pre-service teachers with high, moderate, and low levels of emotional intelligence.
- There is no significant difference in emotional intelligence levels among pre-service teachers with different levels of burnout (low, moderate, and high).

Research Design

This study employed a mixed-methods research design to investigate emotional intelligence and burnout among pre-service teachers. The quantitative part of the study followed a descriptive and correlational research design. This design was used to find the levels of emotional intelligence and burnout and to study the relationship between these two variables. The qualitative part of the study followed a descriptive qualitative research design. This approach was used to understand the signs and causes of burnout, as well as coping strategies and emotional support among peers.

Population

The study population included pre-service teachers enrolled in B.Ed. and M.Ed. programmes. These individuals were studying at two different universities: a central university and a private university. All participants were in the teacher education training stage and had not yet begun teaching professionally.

Sample and Sampling Technique

The sample of the study consisted of 77 pre-service teachers selected from the two universities. The sample included individuals from both B.Ed. and M.Ed. programmes. The participants were selected using convenience sampling, as respondents were chosen based on their availability and willingness to participate in the study.

Research Tools

The following instruments were used for data collection in the present study:

1. Emotional Intelligence Scale (EIS-SANS):

Emotional intelligence was measured using the Emotional Intelligence Scale (EIS-SANS) developed by Dr. Arun Kumar Singh and Dr. Shruti Narain. The scale is a standardized tool widely used in educational research to assess different aspects of emotional intelligence.

2. Burnout Scale:

Burnout was assessed using a self-developed burnout scale constructed by the researchers. The scale consists of 15 items rated on a 5-point Likert scale. Face validity of the scale was established through consultation with subject experts in the field of Education. Based on their suggestions, necessary modifications were made to the items. The burnout scale's reliability was assessed using the test-retest method, and a Pearson correlation coefficient of 0.85 was obtained, indicating satisfactory reliability.

3. Qualitative Tool:

A qualitative tool consisting of open-ended questions was developed to explore the lived experiences of pre-service teachers related to burnout, coping strategies, emotional awareness, and peer support. The development of the qualitative questions was guided by established theoretical frameworks. Coping-related questions were based on the work of Folkman and Lazarus (1988). Questions related to emotional awareness and emotional regulation were informed by the concepts of emotional intelligence proposed by Salovey and Mayer (1990) and Goleman (1995). Burnout-related questions were framed with reference to the explanations provided by Maslach and Leiter (2016). These sources helped identify key areas such as coping behaviours, burnout symptoms, emotional regulation, and emotional responses toward peers, which formed the basis for the final set of open-ended questions.

Quantitative Analysis: Data Analysis and Interpretation

This section presents the statistical analysis and interpretation of emotional intelligence and burnout among pre-service teachers. The analysis includes descriptive statistics, correlation analysis, and one-way ANOVA tests corresponding to the three hypotheses formulated in the study. All analyses were performed using SPSS software.

1. Descriptive Analysis

Descriptive statistics were computed to understand the overall levels of emotional intelligence and burnout among the respondents. As shown in Table 1.1, the mean emotional intelligence score of the sample (N = 77) was 23.06 (SD = 3.90), indicating a moderate EI level. The mean burnout score was 40.35 (SD = 9.60), reflecting a moderate degree of burnout among pre-service teachers.

Table 1.1: Descriptive Statistics of Emotional Intelligence and Burnout

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Emotional Intelligence Score	77	8	29	23.06	3.90
Burnout Score	77	20	60	40.35	9.61
Valid N (listwise)	77				

Hypothesis Wise Analysis and Interpretation

2.1 H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between total emotional intelligence and total burnout among pre-service teachers

To explore this hypothesis, Pearson's product-moment correlation was applied. As shown in Table 1.2, emotional intelligence and burnout are significantly and negatively correlated ($r = -0.440$, $p = 0.001$). This indicates that pre-service Teachers with higher emotional intelligence tend to report lower levels of burnout.

Table 1.2: Correlation between Emotional Intelligence and Burnout

Variable		Emotional Intelligence Score	Burnout Score
Emotional Intelligence Score	Pearson Correlation	1	-0.440
	Sig. (2-tailed)		<0 .001
	N	77	77
Burnout Score	Pearson Correlation	-0.440	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<0.001	
	N	77	77

Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

$$N = 77, p < 0.01$$

Interpretation: The findings demonstrate a meaningful inverse association between the two constructs. Higher emotional intelligence is significantly associated with lower levels of burnout. Since the correlation is statistically significant ($p < 0.05$), the null hypothesis H₀₁ is rejected.

2.2 H₀₂: There is no significant difference in burnout levels among pre-service teachers with high, moderate, and low levels of emotional intelligence.

To test this hypothesis, emotional intelligence scores were categorised into three groups (low, moderate, and high) based on the mean and standard deviation. The burnout mean scores for these groups are presented in Table 1.3. Pre-service teachers with low EI reported the highest burnout, while those with high EI showed the lowest burnout.

Table 1.3: The Burnout Mean Scores

A one-way ANOVA was conducted to examine whether the differences in burnout scores

Burnout Score	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Low Burnout	14	48.7143	10.99
Moderate Burnout	47	39.2553	7.46
High Burnout	16	36.2500	10.25
Total	77	40.3506	9.61

across emotional intelligence levels were statistically significant. As shown in Table 1.4, the differences were found to be significant, $F(2, 74) = 8.459$, $p < 0.001$.

Table 1.4:

Burnout Score	Sum of Squares	Df	F	Sig.
Between Groups	1304.74	2	8.46	<0.001
Within Groups	5706.79	74		
Total	7011.53	76		

To identify exactly where the differences lay, a Tukey post-hoc test was conducted (Table 1.5). The results show that burnout levels in the Low EI group were significantly higher than those in both the Moderate and High EI groups. However, the difference between Moderate and High EI was not statistically significant.

Table 1.5:

Comparison Difference	Mean	Mean Difference	Sig.
Low EI vs Moderate EI	9.46		0.002
Low EI vs High EI	12.46		0.001
Moderate EI vs High EI	3.00		0.467

Significant at $p < 0.05$

Interpretation: The findings suggest that emotional intelligence has a significant impact on burnout. Pre-service teachers with low EI are more vulnerable to burnout, possibly because they struggle with emotional regulation, conflict resolution, and academic stress. Once EI reaches a moderate level, burnout tends to stabilise, which may explain the non-significant difference between the moderate and high EI groups. Thus, the null hypothesis H_{02} is rejected.

2.3 H_{03} : There is no significant difference in emotional intelligence levels among pre-service teachers with different burnout levels (low, moderate, high).

Burnout scores were grouped into three categories using the mean and standard deviation. Table 1.6 illustrates a clear pattern: emotional intelligence consistently decreases as burnout increases. Pre-service teachers with high burnout recorded the lowest EI scores.

Table 1.6: Emotional Intelligence Scores Across Burnout Levels

Burnout Level	N	Mean	EI SD
Low Burnout	13	25.46	3.20
Moderate Burnout	50	23.44	3.11
High Burnout	14	19.50	4.78
Total	77	23.06	3.90

A one-way ANOVA was conducted to test whether these differences were statistically significant. As shown in Table 1.7, the results were significant, $F(2, 74) = 10.709$, $p < .001$.

Table 1.7: ANOVA EI by Burnout Levels

Source	SS	Df	F	Sign
Between Group	259.63	2	10.71	<0 .001
Within Group	897.05	74		

A Tukey post-hoc test (Table 1.8) revealed that the EI scores of pre-service Teachers with high burnout had significantly lower scores than those with both low and moderate burnout. The difference between the low and moderate burnout groups was not significant.

Table 1.8: A Tukey post-hoc test

Comparison	Mean Difference	Sign.
Low vs Moderate	2.02	0.156
Low vs High	5.96	0.000
Moderate vs High	3.94	0.001

Interpretation: The results reveal a clear pattern, where burnout increases, and emotional intelligence tends to decrease. Pre-service teachers experiencing higher burnout may have limited emotional resources, which affects their ability to manage interpersonal situations, control stress, and maintain emotional balance. These findings further strengthen the conclusion that EI and burnout are inversely related. Therefore, the null hypothesis (H_0) is rejected.

Qualitative Analysis: Results and Discussion

The qualitative data collected through open-ended questions were analysed using a thematic analysis approach. All responses were read several times carefully to understand the experiences and views of the participants. Similar responses were grouped together, and repeated ideas were identified. Based on this process, meaningful themes and sub-themes were developed. The analysis focused on understanding burnout experiences, their causes, coping strategies, and preventive measures, as well as emotional support among peers. From the qualitative data, five major themes and related sub-themes emerged. These themes are presented below.

1. Signs of Burnout Recognized by Pre-service Teachers

Participants identified several symptoms through which they understood their state of burnout:

- **Emotional Distress:** "Crying without any reason, body pain, and headache." (P2)
- **Emotional Outburst:** "Outrage, anger, being calm, irritation." (P1)
- **Withdrawal:** Some pre-service teachers said they felt disconnected and avoided academic work or conversations.

These signs indicate both physical and emotional indicators that are linked to burnout from prolonged stress and workload among pre-service teachers.

2. Lived Experiences and Causes of Burnout

Burnout was commonly experienced during pre-service teacher training due to the overlap of academic and personal responsibilities. Participants mentioned that regular coursework, lesson planning, co-curricular tasks, and household duties often led to mental and physical exhaustion.

"I felt burnout while balancing studies with organizing a college fest." (P2)

"Besides regular studies, I felt burnout while managing home responsibilities." (P3)

"Extra workload was too much sometimes." (P5)

The shared accounts show that the cause of burnout was not limited to academic overload but also related to life outside the classroom. It reflects the broader impact of time pressure, multiple commitments, and continuous mental demand.

3. Coping Strategies for Burnout

Pre-service teachers used various personal methods to cope with burnout. These strategies fell under several broad themes:

- **Time Management:** Many participants managed their stress by planning ahead. "Made a timetable and followed it." (P3)
Another emphasized the need to work consistently: "I am always done with my work". (P5)
- **Taking Breaks:** Pre-service teachers highlighted the importance of taking breaks and getting rest. "By taking rest". (P4)
- **Recreational Activities:** Simple daily habits can help with stress relief. For instance, "By listening to songs" (P4) and "I used to take small breaks during studies and go for a walk". (P2)
- **Positive Mindset:** Maintaining calmness and practising control during pressure situations also emerged. "I try to calm myself by drinking water". (P2)

These responses indicate that pre-service teachers employed realistic and accessible strategies, such as planning, resting, and taking moments for themselves to recharge.

4. Strategies for Prevention and Management

In addition to reactive coping, pre-service teachers described how they tried to prevent burnout in the first place:

- **Physical Activity:** "Sometimes I used to go for a walk when I feel exhausted." (P4)
"I participate in extracurricular activities like sports." (P5)
- **Limiting Exposure:** A few avoided activities that felt forced. "By forcing to do." (P4)
- **Self-awareness and Monitoring:** Pre-service teachers shared how they became more aware of their emotional states and took breaks before things worsened.

The data suggests that most participants took basic but effective steps to manage and reduce their stress levels before it escalated into complete burnout.

5. Perceptions and Responses to Peers' Emotions

Pre-service teachers were also asked how they respond to the emotions of their classmates. Their responses indicate high emotional sensitivity and willingness to support others:

- **Emotional Support:** "By talking with them about the problems." (P4)
- **Empathy and Listening:** "I try to often make them laugh or listen to their problems and issues." (P2)
- **Encouragement through Interaction:** "By helping them in their work or by interaction." (P3)

These responses reflect that most pre-service teachers engaged in friendly conversations and informal support as a way of maintaining emotional well-being within their peer group.

Discussion

The findings of the study show a clear pattern between emotional intelligence and burnout among pre-service teachers. The quantitative results revealed moderate levels of both emotional intelligence and burnout. At the same time, a significant negative relationship was found between the two variables. This means that as emotional intelligence increases, burnout decreases. The ANOVA and post-hoc results further confirmed that pre-service teachers with low emotional intelligence experienced the highest levels of burnout, whereas those with moderate and high emotional intelligence reported lower levels of burnout. A similar pattern was observed when emotional intelligence was compared across burnout groups, where higher burnout was linked with lower emotional intelligence.

The qualitative findings help explain why this relationship exists. Pre-service teachers reported that burnout mainly resulted from heavy academic workload, teaching practice, lesson planning, co-curricular responsibilities, and personal or home duties. These overlapping demands created physical tiredness and emotional strain. Many participants described symptoms such as irritation, crying, headaches, and withdrawal from academic activities. These experiences reflect the pressure faced during teacher training.

At the same time, the qualitative responses showed that pre-service teachers actively used simple coping strategies to manage stress. Time planning, taking short breaks, listening to music, going for walks, and talking with peers were commonly mentioned. These strategies suggest that trainees who are more aware of their emotions are better able to manage stressful situations. Their ability to calm themselves and support peers also reflects practical aspects of emotional intelligence in daily life.

When both sets of findings are considered together, it becomes clear that emotional intelligence plays an important role in how pre-service teachers manage stress during training. Those with stronger emotional skills appear more capable of handling academic and personal pressures, while those with lower emotional resources are more likely to experience emotional exhaustion. The discussion therefore supports the view that emotional intelligence is closely linked to burnout and influences how effectively trainees adjust to the demands of teacher education.

Conclusion

The study establishes a clear and significant inverse relationship between emotional intelligence and burnout among pre-service teachers. While participants demonstrated moderate levels of both variables, those with stronger emotional intelligence consistently reported lower burnout. The combined quantitative and qualitative findings indicate that emotional intelligence influences how effectively trainees respond to academic workload, teaching practice demands, and personal responsibilities.

The findings suggest that emotional intelligence serves as an important personal resourceduring teacher education training. Pre-service teachers who are more aware of their emotions and capable of regulating them appear better equipped to manage stress and maintain emotional balance. In contrast, limited emotional skills may increase vulnerability to burnout.Overall, the study underscores the importance of supporting emotional development during the pre-service phase. Strengthening emotional competencies during training may not only reduce burnout but also contribute to healthier, more resilient, and professionally prepared future teachers.

Practical Implications

The study highlights the importance of incorporating emotional intelligence development within pre-service teacher education programmes. Structured opportunities for emotional awareness, stress management, and reflective engagement may help trainees manage academic and professional pressures more effectively. Institutions may consider strengthening access to counselling and mental health support services, while ensuring that teaching practice schedules and academic requirements remain balanced and manageable. Faculty members can contribute by recognizing early signs of burnout and fostering supportive learning environments. Ongoing attention to trainee well-being may enhance both emotional resilience and long-term professional competence.

References

1. Alluru, N. H., & Suneela, M. E. (2023). Emotional competence of pre-service teachers. *International Journal of Novel Research and Development*, 8(12).
2. Folkman, S., & Lazarus, R. S. (1988). *Manual for the Ways of Coping Questionnaire*. Consulting Psychologists Press.
3. Goleman, D. (1995). *Emotional intelligence: Why it can matter more than IQ*. Bantam Books.
4. Gopal, & Jagadeesh, D. H. (2018). Relationship between emotional intelligence and burnout among teacher educators. *International Journal of Indian Psychology*, 6(1). <https://doi.org/10.25215/0601.010>
5. Kant, R., & Shanker, A. (2021). Relationship between emotional intelligence and burnout: An empirical investigation of teacher educators. *International Journal of Evaluation and Research in Education*, 10(3), 966–973. <https://doi.org/10.11591/ijere.v10i3.21255>
6. Ko, C. M. (2015). Mediating effect of stress on relationship between emotional intelligence and burnout among nursing college students. *Journal of the Korean Society of School Health*, 28(3), 239–247. <https://doi.org/10.15434/kssh.2015.28.3.239>

7. Madhur, S. (2017). *Developing intervention strategies for fostering emotional intelligence among pre-service teachers* (Doctoral dissertation, Jamia Millia Islamia).
8. Malakh-Pines, A., & Aronson, E. (1988). *Career burnout: Causes and cures*. Free Press.
9. Maslach, C., & Leiter, M. P. (2016). Understanding the burnout experience: Recent research and its implications for psychiatry. *World Psychiatry, 15*(2), 103–111. <https://doi.org/10.1002/wps.20311>
10. Przybylska, I. (2016). Emotional intelligence and burnout in the teaching profession. *The New Educational Review, 43*(1), 41–51. <https://doi.org/10.15804/ner.2016.43.1.03>
11. Saiiari, A., Moslehi, M., & Valizadeh, R. (2011). Relationship between emotional intelligence and burnout syndrome in sport teachers of secondary schools. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2011.04.003>
12. Salovey, P., & Mayer, J. D. (1990). Emotional intelligence. *Imagination, Cognition and Personality, 9*(3), 185–211. <https://doi.org/10.2190/DUGG-P24E-52WK-6CDG>